

Thyroid

HASHIMOTO'S THYROIDITIS PRESENTING AS GRAVES-BASEDOW DISEASE

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RUNNING TITLE: Hashimoto's thyroiditis presenting as Graves-Basedow disease

KEY WORDS: Hashimoto's thyroiditis, Graves-Basedow, Scintigraphy, Thyroid scan.

For Peer Review

Case report

A 49-year-old woman was referred for assessment of thyroid function after a casual finding of low concentrations of thyrotropin (TSH) (0.001 mUI/mL; normal, 0.350–0.494 mUI/mL) and elevated free thyroxine (FT4) (2.25 ng/dL; normal, 0.70–1.48 ng/dL) in a routine blood test. The patient presented no symptoms of thyroid hyperfunction, and the physical examination showed no goiter or signs of hyperthyroidism. A new blood testing and a thyroid scintigraphy were requested to confirm or to rule out the existence of hyperthyroidism, probably Graves–Basedow disease because of the patient's age and the lack of previous goiter. No treatment was started because she was asymptomatic.

The scintigraphy showed a high asymmetric diffuse uptake without evidence of nodularity compatible with the diagnosis of Graves–Basedow disease (Image 1). Unexpectedly, the blood tests revealed the following concentrations: TSH, 60.949 mIU/mL; FT4, 0.59 ng/dL; thyroid peroxidase (TPO) antibodies, 229 IU/mL (normal, 0–12 IU/mL); and thyroglobulin antibodies, 812 IU/mL (normal, 0–34 IU/mL). The patient remained asymptomatic.

Further blood testing was requested along with thyroid ultrasonography. The thyroid ultrasonography showed a normal thyroid in size and echogenicity without evidence of nodes. The blood test results were: TSH, 23.921 mUI/mL; FT4, 0.68 ng/dL; TPO antibodies, 113 IU/mL; thyroglobulin antibodies, 1093 IU/mL; and thyroid-stimulating immunoglobulin, < 2.5 IU/L (normal 0–14 IU/L). The patient showed no symptoms of thyroid low function. The TSH suppression found in the first blood test was attributed to Hashitoxicosis, the patient was diagnosed with Hashimoto's thyroiditis with hypothyroidism, and she started receiving treatment with levothyroxine 50 µg per day.

After two months of treatment, the blood test and the thyroid scintigraphy were repeated, and the results were: TSH, 2.165 mIU/mL; FT4, 1.23 ng/dL; TPO antibodies, 44 IU/mL; and thyroglobulin antibodies 303 IU/mL. The scintigraphy showed the same high diffuse uptake (Image 2).

Although a thyroid scan is not required to diagnose Hashimoto's thyroiditis, when performed, it can mimic a wide range of thyroid disorders, such as multinodular toxic goiter, functioning adenoma, or, as in our patient, Graves' disease (1, 2).

Taken in isolation, scan findings can be misleading and should be evaluated in conjunction with the clinical profile and blood tests to ensure that a correct diagnosis is made.

References

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Image 1: First thyroid scintigraphy

Image 2: Second thyroid scintigraphy

